

Electrochemical and corrosion studies on electrosynthesised CdInGaSe thin films

R. K. Pathak* and Sandhya Sankwa

Department of Chemistry, Govt. Holkar Science College, Indore-452 017, India

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Preparation of CdInGaSe thin films have been carried out by electrochemical co-deposition method. Photoresponsiveness measurements have been used for the characterization of In and Ga containing CdSe thin films. Variation of capacitance with potential was done in order to see the nature of semiconductivity. Current-voltage measurements were performed for corrosion characteristics. The electrosynthesised films have also been studied in the presence of inhibitor. SEM-EDAX measurements have been used for surface and compositional analysis of the electrodeposited thin films.

Cadmium selenide is one of the promising materials for solar cells. It has a high optical absorption coefficient. The thin film electrosynthesised by electrodeposition is quite attractive for photoelectrochemical (PEC) conversion of solar energy. Cadmium selenide and related materials have received wide attention in the recent years because of their potential use in PEC cells. There has been interest in the use of the semiconductor in PEC applications, since many have band gap suitable for energy conversion¹. There are several methods to prepare photoactive materials. Electrochemical co-deposition method is considered² to be an attractive technique for the formation of such materials. In the present work, electrosynthesis of CdSe, In and Ga containing CdSe thin films have been studied. Photopotential, photocurrent, capacitance measurements, charge carrier concentration and flat band potential have been used for the electrochemical characterization of the films. Polarisation behaviour of the electrodes were performed for the purpose of estimation of corrosion parameters and in presence of inhibitor also³. To ensure the inclusion of In and Ga during deposition of CdSe, EDAX studies was carried out. Scanning Electron Micrographs (SEM) were taken for surface morphology.

Results and discussion

Current-voltage behaviour of the electroplating solution containing 0.1 M CdSO₄ and 0.01 M SeO₂ is shown in Fig. 1. There is a need of suitable deposition potential at which the desired ions may discharge together. On the basis of earlier studies⁴, it has been found that the optimal potential for deposition is -0.600 V vs saturated calomel electrode (SCE). All further preparation of CdSe and CdSe containing different amounts of In and Ga, electrodes were carried out at this potential. The experimental condition for electrosynthesis of CdSe containing

In and Ga are summarized in Table 1.

Variation of current with time during deposition is shown in Fig. 2. The current obtained immediately after

Fig. 1. Current-voltage behaviour of the electrolyte containing 0.1 M CdSO₄ and 0.01 M SeO₂.

application of potential is known to decay with time until a steady state current is achieved. The electrode material markedly affects the current in the study and this can be explained in the term of charge as a probable mechanism. The primary source of charge carriers in the electrode, a contact potential difference is created between two metals – the semiconductor differs from the metal. However in that an electric field may exist within the interior of semiconductor. For this reason the contact potential drop between the metal and semiconductor may take place within the material rather than at contact interface. Along with the field there may exist depletion in the accumulation of charge in the surface layers. The film thickness (F_l) values estimated using the area under I vs t

Table 1. Deposition condition and electrochemical parameters of CdInGaSe thin films

Electroplating solution composition (molar)				(-) Deposition current (mA)		Film thickness (10 ⁻⁵ cm)	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μA)	Flat-band potential (V)	Charge carrier densities (cm ⁻³)
Cd	Se	Ga	In	Initial	Steady state					
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0000	0.569	0.022	0.50	181	9	0.94	2.02 × 10 ¹⁸
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0001	0.835	0.041	1.80	360	12	0.92	2.12 × 10 ¹⁸
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0002	0.860	0.086	2.30	365	16	0.84	2.48 × 10 ¹⁸
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0003	0.886	0.150	3.70	345	34	0.79	3.78 × 10 ¹⁸
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0004	0.915	0.220	3.80	392	65	0.70	4.54 × 10 ¹⁸
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0005	0.960	0.340	9.50	238	23	0.68	3.64 × 10 ¹⁸

Fig. 2. Variation of current with time.

was taken for the duration of deposition according to the relationship

$$F_t = I.t(EW)/F.d.A$$

where I is the current, t is the deposition time, EW is equivalent weight, F is Faraday constant, d is the density and A is the area of electrodeposited films. The ideality factor (n) was calculated using the relationship

$$I = I_0 e^{-ev/nkt}$$

where I_0 is the initial current. The plot of $\log I$ vs V are linear. The ideality factor determined from the slope of the curve $\log I$ vs V is found to be 1. Photoactivity data obtained using electrodeposited electrodes with SCE in the 1 M cadmium acetate, 0.1 M KI and I₂ redox solution are presented in Table 1⁵. The film electrodes become anodic in view of the relatively low cathodic deposition

potential of Se. Its concentration in the electroplating solution was kept equal to 0.01 M while that of Cd equal to 0.1 M. In spite of this there seems to be preponderance of Se in the electrodeposits resulting in p -type semiconductivity.

Capacitance values represent the potential at which no space charge region exists with semiconductor and is usually expressed by the Mott-Schottky (M-S) relationship⁶. Plot of variation of capacitance with potential according to M-S equation is also linear with negative slope. Extrapolation at potential axis to locate flat-band potential and slopes are used to calculate charge carrier densities. The flat band potential and charge carrier densities values are given in the Table 1. The capacitance behaviour indicates that the electrosynthesised films show p -type semiconductivity.

In order to calculate the electrochemical corrosion parameters of the electrodes, variation of current with potential was studied in the redox solution to obtain Tafel plots. The corrosion rate is commonly expressed as

$$C.R. = 0.13. I_{\text{corr}}.(EW)/F.d.A$$

where I_{corr} is corrosion current, EW is equivalent weight, F is Faraday constant, d is density and A is area of deposited material. This equation has been used for the estimation of corrosion rate from corrosion current values obtained from Tafel plots. The corrosion characteristics for different preparation are given in the Table 2. The results presented in Table 2 shows that the CdSe electrode prepared from electroplating solution containing In, Ga in richer amount exhibit enhanced corrosion resistance. In addition to composition, corrosion behaviour of electrodeposits is expected to depend on structural heterogeneity at microscopic level, its porosity and morphological character. A majority of compounds in organic nature are widely used as corrosion inhibitors⁸. In the

Table 2. Corrosion characteristics of CdInGaSe thin films with and without inhibitor (concentration of the inhibitor $2 \times 10^{-4} M$)

Testing solution = $1 M (CH_3COO)_2Cd + 0.1 M KI + 5 mM I_2$

Electroplating solution composition (molar)				Without inhibitor			With inhibitor		
Cd	Se	Ga	In	Polar resistance (KΩ)	Corrosion potential (mV)	Corrosion rate (mpy)	Polar resistance (KΩ)	Corrosion potential (mV)	Corrosion rate (mpy)
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0000	2.25	-0.990	4.96	8.320	0.720	2.10
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0001	2.28	-0.080	4.92	7.500	-0.130	1.99
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0002	0.63	-0.050	3.89	5.710	-0.150	1.49
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0003	3.80	0.034	4.06	7.420	-0.158	1.28
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0004	1.02	0.030	3.85	1.480	-0.142	1.37
0.1	0.01	0.0004	0.0005	1.14	0.120	1.49	1.840	-0.850	1.44

present study we have seen the action and effectiveness of benzotriazole as inhibitor for the corrosion of electrodeposited thin films. Photoactivity has also been studied in the presence of inhibitor. The corrosion and inhibition processes were examined at room temperature. Fig. 3 shows the results of polarization measurement in presence and in absence of inhibitor. Both anodic and cathodic current decreases in the presence of inhibitor. However the Tafel slopes are not changed the corrosion potential and are displaced to more positive values. These observations suggest that the film formed in the presence of inhibitor acts through a blocking effect mainly on anodic reaction. This indicates that the inhibitive efficiency depends on the structure of protective film formed by dissolved substance.

Figs. 4 and 5 shows the scanning electron micrograph (SEM) with magnification 500x, 2000x for CdSe and

Fig. 3. Polarisation curve : (●) in presence and (◆) in absence of inhibitor.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. Scanning electron micrograph of CdSe : (a) magnification 500x and (b) magnification 2000x.

CdInGaSe respectively. The micrographs show a uniform morphology with grain size of the order of $10 \mu m$. The amount of deposits of CdSe containing In, Ga is larger than that of CdSe. To ensure the inclusion of In and Ga during electrodeposition of CdSe, EDAX studies were carried out. A comparison between the compositions of Cd, Se, In and Ga in the electrodeposited film to electroplating solution is given in Table 3. This confirms that the incorporation of In and Ga to CdSe and inclusion are accompanied by a substantial decrease in Se content.

On the basis of studies presented here in it may be inferred that electrosynthesis of CdSe containing In and

Fig. 5. Scanning electron micrograph of CdInGaSe : (a) magnification 500x and (b) magnification 2000x.

Table 3. A comparison of chemical composition of the quantity present in electroplating solution and in electrodeposited thin films (EDAX)

Element present	Cd	Se	Ga	In
Electroplating solution (wt%)	98.51	1.42	0.035	0.033
Electrodeposited thin film (wt%)	41.80	32.46	23.51	2.23

Ga have increased photoactivity and corrosion resistance. Electrochemical inclusion of inhibitor leads to further improvement in corrosion resistance.

Experimental

Thin films of CdSe and CdSe containing In, Ga have been prepared from aqueous solution of CdSO_4 , SeO_2 , GaNO_3 , InCl_3 by cathodic deposition on titanium substrate using three-electrode configuration. Deposition was carried out at room temperature at constant potential. 1×1 cm titanium plate were attached to one side with thick copper wire using silver epoxy for ohmic contact and rest of the portion protected with araldite for insulation. These plates were cleaned with emery paper, washed with acetone and distilled water. For electrodeposition, two titanium electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) dipped in the electroplating solution for equilibration. In the cell, one titanium electrode act as a working, another as a counter and SCE as a reference electrode.

Power supply (Systronics) was used as a power source and digital multimeters (Systronics) were used for the measurements of current-voltage. Variation of capacitance with potential were studied with the help of LCR meter (Systronics). Current-voltage behaviour of the deposited films in the electrolytic solution of cadmium acetate, KI and I_2 have been studied for corrosion characteristics. SEM (suzo camera model) along with EDAX (kuex) have been used for surface and compositional analysis.

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